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SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
AND FOOD PRODUCTION<<**

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Mirela Rehić (Head of the Library)
Faculty of Technology, University in Tuzla
Urfeta Vejzagića 8, 75000 Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina
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LINEAR AND NON-LINEAR ECOTOXICOLOGY MODELING OF THE SERIES OF 1,3,5-TRIAZINE DERIVATIVES

BY BENJAMIN SALAKOVIĆ[✉], STRAHINJA KOVAČEVIĆ, MILICA KARADŽIĆ

BANJAC, SANJA PODUNAVAC-KUZMANOVIĆ, LIDIJA JEVRIC

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

[✉] benjamin.salakovic@uns.ac.rs

The widespread use of pesticides has led to the significant environmental pollution. Designing new pesticides is one of the important tasks in recent scientific research. Prediction and determination of their ecotoxicity is of great importance for environmental impact assessment. The present study is focused on the prediction of some *in silico* ecotoxicity parameters, including acute algae toxicity, acute daphnia toxicity, *Daphnia magna* LC50 48h/EPA and *Daphnia magna* LC50 48h/DEMETRA, of a series consisting of twenty-one 1,3,5-triazine derivatives. The modeling was done based on the physicochemical molecular descriptors that were used as independent variables while the ecotoxicity parameters were dependent variables. The modeling was based on Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) approach with linear and non-linear regression. The selection of the subset of molecular descriptors was done by stepwise selection procedure. Linear modeling was carried out by using multiple linear regression and non-linear modeling by artificial neural networks. The obtained models were validated by internal and external validation and their high predictive ability was confirmed. The established QSAR models successfully correlate particular molecular features with ecotoxicity data of 1,3,5-triazine derivatives and enable easy and quick prediction of their ecotoxicity.

Keywords: pesticides; chemometrics; molecular modeling; ecotoxicology; QSAR

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Environmental Monitoring and Management

REMOVAL OF PHARMACEUTICALS FROM WATER BY NANOFILTRATION MEMBRANES

BY JELENA ŠURLAN[✉], NIKOLA MARAVIĆ, IGOR ANTIĆ, NATAŠA ĐURIŠIĆ-

MLADENOVIĆ, JELENA ŽIVANČEV, BILJANA PAJIN, ŽITA ŠEREŠ

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

[✉] jelena.surlan@uns.ac.rs

Pharmaceuticals found in aquatic environment have adverse effects on human health and the environment. Traditional wastewater treatments are inefficient in the removal of pharmaceutical compounds, therefore, additional processes, such as nanofiltration, are required. The aim of this study was to compare removal efficiencies of selected pharmaceuticals from water solution using two polyamide nanofiltration membranes with different molecular weight cut offs (MWCO), 200 Da and 400 Da. Dead-end nanofiltration experiments with both membranes were conducted at the same value of membrane flux. The lowest rejection rates were observed for the pharmaceutical with the lowest molecular weight, acetaminophen (151.16 g/mol), compared to carbamazepine and salbutamol with molecular weights of 236.27 g/mol and 239.31 g/mol, respectively. Rejection rates for acetaminophen, carbamazepine and salbutamol were 76.24%, 94.36% and 94.18%, respectively, with nanofiltration membrane with lower MWCO (200 Da). However, lower rejection rates were observed using the membrane with higher MWCO (400 Da), with values of 61.32%, 92.85% and 68.97% for acetaminophen, carbamazepine and salbutamol, respectively.

Keywords: pharmaceuticals; membrane processes; nanofiltration; water treatment

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